

Fire-and-Forget Distributed Function Execution with funcX

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Federated Function as a Service

- Modern computing environments are distributed and heterogeneous; modern workloads require specialized hardware, rapid responses, and remote processing (e.g., near data)
- FaaS provides an intuitive interface for users to register and invoke programming functions without regard for underlying infrastructure
- Federated FaaS enables functions to be dispatched to remote endpoints chosen for data locality, security, or other concerns
- funcX allows users to execute Python functions (which may invoke executables, MPI programs, etc.) on arbitrary resources (e.g., CPUs, GPUs) from short to long run times

Fire-and-forget execution

Outsource the challenging aspects of remote execution

funcX manages authentication, serialization of functions and data, reliable execution optionally in containers, and delivery of results back to requesting users

Transform resources into FaaS endpoints

Easily manage execution across distributed resources

The funcX endpoint software can be deployed on laptops, clouds, clusters, and supercomputers. It provisions resources elastically based on workload.

- (1) Registration** (function + container)
- (2) Execution** (function, endpoint, args)

```
def compute(args):
    # do something
    return results
```


High performance

Launch millions of tasks

funcX supports batch submission and monitoring, asynchronous callbacks, container warming, automated resource scaling, fault tolerance, prefetching, and memoization

Application examples

Install and configure a funcX endpoint


```
$ pip install funcx_endpoint
$ funcx-endpoint configure
$ funcx-endpoint start <ENDPOINT_NAME>
```

Instantiate a funcX client

```
from funcx.sdk.client import FuncXClient

fxc = FuncXClient()
```

Register Python function with input args

```
def hello_world():
    return "Hello World!"

func_uuid = fxc.register_function(hello_world)
```

Execute a function by specifying endpoint and input arguments

```
ep_id = '4b116d3c-1703-4f8f-9f6f-39921e5864df'
result = fxc.run(endpoint_id=ep_id,
                 function_id=func_uuid)
```

Retrieve results (and exceptions) asynchronously

```
fxc.get_result(result)
```


Try on Binder
<https://funcx.org/binder>